

DESIGN OF LINEAR ARRAY OF H-PLANE SECTORAL HORNS WITH LOW SIDE LOBE LEVEL

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Abstract:

Side Lobe Level is one of the important parameters of the array antennas used in the electronic systems like radars, jammers, satellite transponders, trackers, etc., The Side Lobe Level is generally not constant over the operating frequency range of array antennas. In this paper, a linear array of horns with low side lobe level is designed, simulated and measured. The simulated results are compared with measured results and are in agreement.

Indexed Terms: Band Width Ratio (BWR), Electronic Warfare, Impedance, Side Lobe Level & Ultra Wide Band (U.W.B)

1. Introduction:

Radar and Electronic Warfare (E.W) systems are ultra-wideband systems that operate in thousands of MHz of bandwidth [1]. Electronic Support Measures (E.S.M) and Electronic Counter Measures (E.C.M) are part of E.W [2]. E.C.M systems are configured with high power transmitters, consisting of T.W.T Amplifier (T.W.T.A) or Solid State Power Amplifier (S.S.P.A) and highly directive and electronically steerable antenna. The antenna shall withstand high power R.F signals, requiring excellent matching of 50Ω with free space impedance (Z_0) of $120\pi \Omega$. The active V.S.W.R of the array is very critical parameter for such applications and depends on V.S.W.R of the element. The other important parameter is side lobe level (S.L.L). Many engineers have experimented with standard techniques to improve the side lobe level of the arrays, but these are applicable to narrow band applications. Hence new technique is proposed in this paper to reduce the side lobe level. The design, simulation, fabrication and validation is carried out the details are presented in the paper.

2. Techniques for Reduction of S.L.L:

Side Lobe Level is one of the important specifications for antennas in radar and E.W applications. Many techniques have been proposed by antenna engineers to reduce the S.L.L such as dual mode, multimode excitations and dielectric loading (Dielectric guides) near the aperture and in between walls of the horns [1 – 3]. These methods are very effective for reduction of S.L.L, but the gain is marginally reduced due to widening of the major and minor beams. To overcome this problem, a new technique is simulated and published by Ronaldo O. dos Santos and Carlos Leonidas da S. S. Sobrinho [4]. These authors have shown the improvement graphically in the S.L.L of H-plane sectoral horn by placing dielectric slabs in the horn body at different distances from the vertex, but the practical implementation is not evident. The simulation results published by these authors are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Influence on S.L.L due to introduction of dielectric slab inside the horn [4]

3. Design Specifications & Simulations:

3.1 Specifications of Array: The specifications of linear array of H-plane sectoral horns with 8 elements are given at Table 1.

Table 1: Design Specifications of Linear Array

S.No	Parameter	Linear array of H-plane sectoral horns
1.	Frequency range	6-18 GHz

2.	No of elements	8
3.	V.S.W.R Max.	2.5:1
4.	Gain (Min.)	15.8 dBi
5.	Side Lobe Level	-10 dBc
6.	3-dB beam width (Az & El)	5-20°
7.	Power handling of element	100 Watts CW

3.2 Design Calculations of the Element: Based on the above requirements, the design parameters of H-plane sectoral horn element at 6 GHz are calculated and given at Table-2. The simulation and measurement of V.S.W.R, gain of the array of H-plane sectoral horns are presented in [9]. The improvements of the array in V.S.W.R by 0.3 (from 3.0 to 2.7) and gain by 0.44 dB (from 14.04 to 14.48 dBi) is demonstrated with hybrid tapering of antenna plates [9]. The V.S.W.R is further improved by using dual wire loading and the gain is improved by insertion of parabolic dielectric lens in the horn. The design parameters of sectoral horn used for linear array of sectoral horns is shown at Table-2.

Table 2: Design Calculations of the Element

D_H (dBi)	D_H	G_H	X	A	R_0	l_H
6.5	4.2	70	7.3 mm	136.4mm	344.6 mm	351.3 mm

3.3 Simulation of Array: The arrangement of the elements of the array of H-plane sectoral horns is shown at “Figure-3”.

Figure 3: Arrangement of elements of linear array of H-plane sectoral horns

The array is simulated using CST studio Ver 12 and the simulated model is shown below at Figure-4 and 5. In the simulation, the dielectric slabs made up of Teflon are used on inner side of the horn plates.

Figure 4: Simulation of plate of linear array of horns with dielectric slabs on the walls of the antenna plates

Figure 5: Simulated array Model

The material characteristics of the dielectric slabs are as follows.

- ✓ Material Teflon (PTFE) (lossy)
- ✓ Epsilon 2.1
- ✓ Mue 1
- ✓ El. tand 0.0002 (Const. fit)

- ✓ Rho 2200 [kg/m³]
- ✓ Thermal conductivity 0.2 [W/K/m]
- ✓ Heat cap. 1 [kJ/K/kg]
- ✓ Diffusivity 9.09091e-008 [m²/s]
- ✓ Young's Mod. 0.5 [kN/mm²]
- ✓ Poisson Ratio 0.4
- ✓ Thermal Exp. 140 [1e-6/K]

3.4 Simulation Results: The simulation results of V.S.W.R over 6 to 18 GHz after insertion of dielectric slabs is shown at Figure-6.

Figure 6: Simulated V.S.W.R after insertion of dielectric slabs

The simulation results of Gain over 6 to 18 GHz is shown at Figure-7.

Figure 7: Simulated Gain after insertion of dielectric slabs

The simulation results of radiation pattern over 6 to 18 GHz after insertion of dielectric slabs is shown at Figure-8 to 14.

Figure 8: Simulated radiation pattern at 6 GHz

Figure 9: Simulated radiation pattern at 8 GHz

Figure 10: Simulated radiation pattern at 10 GHz

Figure 11: Simulated radiation pattern at 12 GHz

Figure 12: Simulated radiation pattern at 14 GHz

Figure 13: Simulated radiation pattern at 16 GHz

Figure 14: Simulated radiation pattern at 18 GHz

The S.L.L is calculated from the radiation pattern over 6 to 18 GHz and is tabulated in Table-6.1.

Table 3: Simulated Results of S.L.L

S.No	Frequency in GHz	S.L.L in E.P. (dB)
1	6.0	-22.4
3	8.0	-23.6

5	10.0	-21.6
7	12.0	-21.3
9	14.0	-22.2
10	15.0	-23.0
13	18.0	-23.0

4. Fabrication and Measurements:

4.1 Fabrication: The dielectric slabs have been manufactured and assembled in to the plates of the linear array of sectoral horn elements and the testing has been carried out and the results are shown below.

4.2 Measurement Results:

4.2.1 V.S.W.R Measurements: The V.S.W.R measured for one element after introducing the dielectric slabs are shown at Figure-15.

Figure 15: Measured V.S.W.R

4.2.2 Radiation Pattern Measurements: The radiation patterns measured after above modifications have been carried out and the plots are shown in Figure-16 to Figure-22.

Figure 16: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 6 GHz

Figure 17: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 8 GHz

Figure 18: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 10 GHz

Figure 19: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 12 GHz

Figure 20: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 14 GHz

Figure 21: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 16 GHz

Figure 22: Measured Radiation pattern with dielectric slabs – 18 GHz

Form the radiation patterns, the side lobe level calculated and tabulated at Table-4.

Table 4: Measured Results of S.L.L

S.No	Frequency in GHz	S.L.L in E.P. (dB)
1	6.0	-14.5
3	8.0	-12.5
5	10.0	-9.0
7	12.0	-12.5
9	14.0	-18.0
10	15.0	-17
13	18.0	-13.0

The degradation of S.L.L at 10 GHz is observed due to limitation in the measurement setup.

5. Conclusion:

A linear array with eight sectoral horn elements with insertion of dielectric slabs is designed, simulated, manufactured and tested for Side lobe level. The simulation and measurements are also carried out for V.S.W.R and Gain to ensure that there is no degradation in these specifications due to insertion of dielectric slabs. It is concluded that the simulated and measured results are meeting all the design specifications.

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